

FUNDED – HE board game

TOOLSHEET

Purpose

Funded (2022) is a board game for 2 to 6 players/teams about the Horizon Europe framework programme, in an entertaining way. Convert your project idea from its conceptual stage into a successful European funded project, taking it throughout the whole cycle of Horizon Europe, from proposal submission to project justification.

Benefits

Test your knowledge and jargon on Horizon Europe project proposal requirements and issues. You will learn in a playful way about the numerous nuances of Horizon Europe.

Practical recommendations

Download and read instructions (15 min)

Download the material from the website (link in the orange box). Read the 2 pages of instructions.

Find 1-5 other players and set a time to play for 1h-1h30 (x min)

Prepare the materials (15 min)

Print the materials, collect objects as meeples (1 p/p) and 2 dices.

Play! (90 min)

Explain the rules to everyone and play!

Applicability box

Main MA Skill supported

Gain experience with multi-actor methods and/or practicalities.

Relevant Target groups

Useful link(s)*

[Link to download the materials](#)

*right click to open

Figure 1: Game Board

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Funded by
the European Union